

The Monastery of Mangana

also known as “The Monastery of St. George of the Mangana”

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Entry tags: Constantinople, Christianity, Archaeological Site, Religious Group, Byzantine, Monastery, City, Mausoleum, Religious Place, Orthodoxy, Shrine, Private residence, Monument

The Monastery of St. George of the Mangana was a monastery founded on the easternmost extremity of the Constantinopolitan peninsula on the acropolis of ancient Byzantium in the vicinity of a formal Arsenal for siege weapons (Mangana), by Constantine IX Monomachos in the eleventh century, as part of a complex which included an imperial palace, a hospital, a law school, and various hostels for the indigent and the infirm, as well as extensive gardens. Michael Psellos, in his description of the Mangana complex which is incorporated into his famous *Chronographia*, describes a complex of elegant and richly ornamented buildings decorated with gilded motifs of stars and set on a level terrace amid verdant parkland and water features. The future ecumenical patriarch, Constantine Leichoudes, was given the pronoia of Mangana, though the exact nature of this grant is difficult to ascertain. Needless to say, it was following a swim in one of these ornamental ponds at the complex that the founder and builder of the complex, Constantine IX Monomachos, would die of pleurisy and be buried in the complex alongside his mistress Skleraina. Following an interval of more than a hundred years, during which the richly endowed complex presumably continued to prosper, during the reign of Isaac II Angelos at the end of the twelfth century, it seems that much of the complex save the monastery itself was demolished to provide building material for the Church of the Archangel Michael at Anaplous further along the Bosphorus. Following an occupation by Latin monks following the Fourth Crusade, the monastery went on to play an important role in Byzantine ecclesiastical politics in the Palaiologan era, serving as the location of a Synod in 1279, and as the place of retirement of John VI Kantakouzenos in the 1350's. Following the Ottoman Conquest of Constantinople, the building was repurposed as a dervish convent, before being leveled to accommodate the construction of the Topkapi Palace in the 1460's. In 1871 a portion of its ruins were destroyed during the construction of a railway. In the early 1920's during the occupation of Istanbul in the aftermath of World War I, the substructures of the building were excavated by the French military and their contours recorded by archaeologists, the findings of whom suggested a cross-in-square church of sizable dimensions with an adjoining portico and perhaps a freestanding octagonal chapel beside it. These remains still exist in some form, though inaccessible to the public in a closed off area of the Topkapi Palace.

Date Range: 1050 CE - 1460 CE

Region: Constantinople, c800CE-1400CE

Region tags: Byzantium

Constantinople, c800CE-1400CE

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ernest Mamboury and Robert Demangel, *Le quartier des Manganes et la première région de Constantinople* (Paris, de Boccard 1939).
- Source 2: Ewan Short, Maria, Monomachos, and the Mangana: Imperial Legitimacy (1042-1046), in the *Scandinavian Journal of Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* vol. 6 (2020), 9-54.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.thebyzantinelegacy.com/georgios-mangana>
- Source 1 Description: <https://www.byzantium1200.com/georgios.html>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1922-1923

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: French Military Excavation of the Mangana District, 1922-1923.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Body of water (as distinct from source)
- Other [specify]: The Bosphorus

Type of elevation

- Hill
- Other [specify]: The Acropolis of Old Byzantium

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Terracing
- Clearing
- Water feature
- Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It can be assumed that it was enclosed in some capacity like most urban monasteries, but whether this constituted an actual separation from the rest of the urban fabric is debatable.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The original complex would have included residential, educational, and service facilities, as well as the monastery itself and its adjoining complex.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: In Byzantine times it was part of the district of Mangana, but in the Ottoman period it was enclosed within the Topkapi Palace.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Healing

Notes: There was a hospital and various xenodochia endowed as part of the complex.

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Memorial

Notes: It was a major imperial project of Konstantinos Monomachos and was intended as an imperial mausoleum.

– Political

– Social

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: Demolished

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Christ

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Imperial Legitimacy

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We know very little about the relationship between the buildings within the complex owing to the small scale of the excavations.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We know very little about the relationship between the buildings within the complex owing to the small scale of the excavations.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It can be assumed that it was quite a sizeable edifice, though Byzantine architecture of the 11th and 12th centuries might be said to possess a human rather than a monumental scale.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– I don't know

Notes: We do not know the specifics of its construction, though it would be safe to conjecture that it was constructed of a mixture of brick and stone, at least as regards the primary buildings.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably brick and ceramic were utilized.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
– Yes
Notes: A plaque of the Virgin was discovered in a cistern at Mangana.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:
– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other type of decoration:
– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:
– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably corpses were prepared for burial in the attached hospitals and xenodochia, but it cannot be said to be a primary function of the place.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Imperial burials of Konstantinos Monomachos, Skleraina, etc.

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: I would argue no more or less than any other Byzantine Church. We have no evidence of any particular cult being imputed to it as at Blachernai.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to reconstruct the ritual use of the building.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to reconstruct the ritual use of the building in any specific way.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: N/A

Notes: It is difficult to reconstruct the ritual use of the building.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: N/A

Notes: It is difficult to reconstruct the ritual use of the building, though presumably the monks in the Monastery followed the Byzantine liturgical calendar.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Communion Wine

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We know very little about the relationship between the buildings within the complex and their character owing to the small scale of the excavations.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It seems more likely that St. George of the Mangana was primarily a monastic rather than a congregational church, though that does not exclude lay presence and participation in certain guises.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– Field doesn't know

↳ Healing magic

– Field doesn't know

↳ Cleansing

– Yes

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Expiation
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Hospital Facilities

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Monks

↳ Present full time
– Yes

↳ Present part time
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– Yes

- ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:
 - Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably monks spent their formative years here, but it is difficult to confirm that this was the case, or what the background of its inhabitants was.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

- ↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably there were bureaucrats attached to the palace as well as the law school, as well as monks who performed bureaucratic roles within the monastic community.

- ↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

- ↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know the reality of how the monastery supported itself, though by analogy with other Byzantine monasteries it was likely endowed with significant urban and rural properties.

- ↳ Does this place lease out land:
 - Field doesn't know

Notes: It is impossible to confirm this, but likely that they did.

- ↳ Does this place lease out tools:
 - Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

- ↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
 - Yes

Notes: This was typical for Byzantine monasteries at least in some capacity, and the xenodochia, hospitals, and hostels almost certainly dispensed material charity.

- ↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
 - Field doesn't know

Notes: More research needs to be done on urban monasteries as loci of civic life.

- ↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
 - Yes

Notes: A law school was present.

- ↳ Function for water management:
 - Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not unlikely that the water features of the complex also served the population of the district.

- ↳ Part of the transportation network:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Monastery of Mangana, Mamboury, Ernest, and Robert Demangel. *Le Quartier Des Manges Et La Première Région De Constantinople*. Paris: de Boccard, 1939.

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